

Somewhere along the way, the worlds of the universe change into the worlds of the verse.

There are two nordic worlds, the first, the absolute finally perpetually something world, the accepteknee existeknee world, where the only thing that exists is my knees, and the only thing I accept is my knees. The second is the imaginary world, where it's all in the head of myself, and the things I imagine in my head have no correlation to the things that are actually happening and actually just are. The absolutely finally perpetually something world changes into the fantasy world, and the absolutely finally perpetually nothing world changes into the dream world. Currently, all things are imaginary in the nordic world, the trees are imaginary, what I see in the mirror is imaginary, my toes are imaginary, food is imaginary, problems are imaginary, solutions are imaginary, houses are imaginary, and to become successful in this world is to have the most obnoxious imagination, and to deny all that there is, flying in the face of evidence.

The frankish world is the public world, where for some reason I'm without my garment.

The asian world is the den world, where you get stalled.

The spanish world is the world of carts, but hush I'll tell you a secret.

The italian world is the breakdown world, where getting something repaired is secondary.

The slavic world is the communal world, where what's yours, is mine.

The turkish world is the monumental world, where the greatest monument one can erect, is the monument to stan.

The pacific islander world is the world of doodles, where idling is expected.

The german world is the world of civilizations that are anything but civilised, it is the world of rebuttals.

The romanian world is the world of high stakes.

The indian world is the world of doctored reports.

The british world is the world of merry-go-rounds, where buzzwords like "I'm shocked", "I'm apauled", "you get toime", and "he gets a shake" are expected, and where a phrase is the most valuable currency there is.

The arabic world is the world of terrorists.

The african world is the world of burns, where black eventually cracks.